

Job Satisfaction Facet Company Policies and Practices of Public and Private Universities Teachers in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan

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Abstract

Organizations claim to make policy changes for betterment in the workplace, improving operations or creating a safer environment for employees. But employees' initial reaction is often resistance to these changes unless they are convinced with the claim. This paper compares the opinions of teaching faculty of public and private universities on company policy and practices, sub

Key Words

Job Satisfaction,
Teaching Faculty,
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and Practices

variable of job satisfaction. The population contained all teaching faculty of universities in KP province. For drawing sample, universities selection was done randomly. Fourteen universities were selected through simple random sampling method out of 30 universities. 420 respondents were randomly selected from the population. Data collection was done through Minnesota Questionnaire. Insignificant difference is reported between the opinions of teaching faculty of these two sector universities on company policy and practices domain of their job satisfaction.

Introduction

Job satisfaction shows opinions and feelings of an employee about his job, work environment, and the organization. Various scholars have defined the job satisfaction in different ways. Job satisfaction measures employee's connectedness with the organization.

Weiss (2002) stated that job satisfaction was an attitude. Work satisfaction of employees of an organization is done by various factors. These are management styles, workers participation, delegation of authority, salaries, responsibilities, upgradation opportunities, the nature of work. Social and cultural environment also play important role.

Teachers are builder of a nation. They play important role in development of a nation. Good teachers produce good leaders for a nation. They transmit knowledge to the students and make them capable of taking responsibilities of a nation. That is why teachers' job satisfaction is very essential. If they are satisfied, they will properly deliver and maximum result will be obtained. Kuhn (1980) and Plessman (1986) found that factors which satisfy or dissatisfy a teacher take place in patterns. These factors were correlated with specific personality types. Teachers job dissatisfiers should remove. If removal of these factors is not possible, then steps should be taken to minimize the impact of these factors. The study at hand gives an account of job satisfaction of teaching faculty of institutions of higher education of Pakistan in general and in particular in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Work satisfaction of teaching faculty of universities is influenced by several factors.

These factors may be teachers' ability use, performance, promotion, empowerment, salaries, relation with co-workers, relation with administration officers, physical facilities etc. This study specially focusses on university policy and practices domain. Comparison has been done of the opinions of teaching faculty of public and private universities through academic qualification, designation and work experience on university policy and practices.

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Kaur and Sidana (2011) reported comparison of job satisfaction of educators by gender.

They found that work satisfaction level of male educators was higher than female educators. Gupta, Pasrija and Bansal (2012) studies job satisfaction of teachers. They found that job satisfaction level of female educators was higher than the male educators. This study also investigated job satisfaction of educators of urban and rural areas. The finding was that educators of rural schools were more satisfied as compared to educators of schools located in urban areas. Bashir and Ramay (2008) found correlation between variables career opportunities and work life policies and organization commitment among IT professional. But there was no correlation between their job characteristics and organizational commitment.

Teachers who are satisfied with their job make an educational institution a successful one. There are some factors in educational institutions which causes anxiety among teachers. Ferguson et al (2012) found that workload and work conditions predicted anxiety among teachers. They further stated that stress and depression had negative effect on their job satisfaction. While their teaching experience had positive effect on their work satisfaction.

Abdullah *et al* (2009) investigate work satisfaction level among secondary school educators. They reported that male educators felt more satisfaction than their female counterparts. Educators having bachelor degree showed more satisfaction about their job as compared to those educators who did not have bachelor degree. They further reported that educators with more length of work experience showed high level of work satisfaction compared to those who had comparatively little experience. Hettiarachchi (2014) explored the effect of job satisfaction on IT professionals job performance. Job satisfaction variable contained sub variable. The sub variables were pay, promotion, supervision and work. The study further reported that there existed positive correlation among job satisfaction four sub variables and IT professional job performance in Srilanka. Tella et al (2007) investigated relationship among organizational motivation, work satisfaction and commitment. They found negative correlation between motivation and commitment. They further investigate comparison between opinions of technical and non-technical library staff regarding their perceived motivation. There was insignificant difference between the opinions of professional and non-professional staff of library about motivation.

Objectives of the Study

1. To conduct comparison of the opinions of teaching faculty of public and private sector universities regarding company policy and practices domain of job satisfaction.
2. To conduct comparison of the opinions of teaching faculty of public and private sector universities through academic qualification regarding company policy and practices domain of job satisfaction.
3. To compare views of teaching faculty of public and private sector universities through designation regarding company policy and practices domain of job satisfaction.
4. To conduct comparison of the opinions of teaching faculty of public and private sector universities through work experience regarding company policy and practices domain of job satisfaction.

Design of th Study

Questionnaire was employed for data collection. The study was descriptive. Survey was done. The study design was survey method.

The study nature was descriptive. The researcher used survey method design for the study. So, survey method design was used for the study.

Population and Sample

All teaching faculty of universities in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa comprised population of the study. There were 30

universities in province of KP. Fourteen universities were randomly selected out of 30 by the researcher. The respondent's selection was done randomly by the researcher. In that way 30 teachers were randomly selected from each university. The sample size was 420 teachers.

Data Collection Instrument

For data collection, the researcher used Minnesota Questionnaire. For the Minnesota Questionnaire use, the researcher paid in dollar to Institute of Vocational Psychology, Minnesota University, United States of America. For data collection, the researcher personally visited the selected universities and distributed the copies of questionnaire among respondents. Before questionnaire distribution among respondents, permission was got from relevant heads of departments.

Data Analysis Techniques

Data collected through Minnesota Questionnaire, was put into SPSS. For the data analysis, Mean, Std, and Independent Samples t-test was employed.

Results

The study conducts on the comparison of job satisfaction domain company policy and practices of teaching faculty of public and private universities in province of KP. Three demographic variables, i-e, academic qualification, designation, teaching experience have been included for comparison. Four tables are given below. The tables contain figures. These tables are properly interpreted.

Table 1. Shows Views Comparison of Teachers of Govt: and Private Sector Universities on Company Policy and Practices

Teaching Faculty	Universities	N	Mean	Std	t-value
Educators	Govt:	209	15.30	1.88	16.70
	Private	160	11.02	2.44	

Table 1 reflects contrast of views between teaching faculty of public and private universities on company policy and practice. The Mean values of public and private universities teaching faculty are 15.30, 11.302 with std 1.18, 2.44 respectively. T-value is 16.70. P-value which is .762 is higher than .05 which shows insignificant difference between the views of teaching faculty of Govt: sector and private sector universities. Mean value of public sector universities is 15.30 which shows that teaching faculty of public sector universities are more satisfied than private universities on company policy and practice domain of job satisfaction.

Table 2. Opinions Comparison of Teaching Faculty of Public and Private Universities on Company Policy and Practice through Qualification

Academic Qualification	Universities	N	Mean	Std	t-value
M.Phil Qualification	Govt:	56	15.23	0.77	8.77
	Private	40	11.33	2.11	
Ph.D Qualification	Govt:	47	14.93	0.546	7.11
	Private	22	11.04	2.88	

Table 2 shows contrast between opinions of teaching faculty of public and private universities through academic qualification on company policy and practice. The Mean values of public and private universities teaching faculty of M.Phil qualification are 15.23, 11.33 with std .77, 2.11 respectively. T-value is 8.77. P-value which is .55 is higher than .05 which reflects insignificant contrast between the views of faculty of Govt: sector and private sector universities through M.Phil qualification. Mean value of public sector universities is 15.23 which shows that teaching faculty of M.Phil qualification of public sector universities are more satisfied than private universities on company policy and practice domain of job satisfaction. The Mean values of public and private universities teaching faculty of PhD qualification are 14.93, 11.04 with std .546, 2.88 respectively. T-value is 6.21. P-value which is .59 is higher than .05 which shows that there is insignificant difference between the opinions of teaching faculty of Govt: sector and private universities through PhD degree. Mean value of public sector universities is 14.93 which shows that teaching faculty of PhD qualification of public sector universities are more satisfied than private universities on company policy and practice domain of job satisfaction.

Table 3. Shows Views Difference of Teachers of Govt: Sector and Private Universities on Company Policy and Practices through Designation

Designation	Universities	N	Mean	Std	t-value
Lecturer	Govt:	137	15.44	1.30	14.33
	Private	116	9.99	2.32	
Assistant professor	Govt:	47	15.66	.507	10.22
	Private	23	11.22	1.42	
Associate professor	Govt:	13	15.10	.22	5.76
	Private	12	10.30	2.05	

The above table 3 reflects opinions comparison of teachers of Govt: sector and private sector universities through designation on company policy and practice. The Mean values of public and private universities teaching faculty of lecturer designation are 15.44, 9.99 with std 1.30, 2.32 respectively. T-value is 14.33. P-value which is .55 is higher than .05 which shows insignificant difference between the opinions of teaching faculty of lecturer designation of public and private universities about job satisfaction domain company policy and practices. Mean value of public sector universities lecturers is 15.44 which shows that teaching faculty of lecturer designation of public sector universities are more satisfied than private universities on company policy and practice domain of job satisfaction. The Mean values of public and private universities teaching faculty of assistant professor designation are 15.66, 11.22 with std .507, 1.42 respectively. T-value is 10.22. P-value which is .59 is higher than .05 which reflects insignificant difference between the opinions of teaching faculty of assistant professor designation of Govt: sector and private sector universities regarding job satisfaction domain company policy and practices. The Mean values of public and private universities teaching faculty of associate professor designation are 15.10, 10.30 with std .22, 2.05 respectively. T-value is 5.76. P-value which is .65 is higher than .05 which reflects insignificant difference between the opinions of teaching faculty of associate professor designation of public and private universities about job satisfaction domain company policy and practices. Mean value of public sector universities associate professor is 15.10 which shows that teaching faculty of associate professor designation of public sector universities are more satisfied than private universities on company policy and practice domain of job satisfaction.

Table 4. Shows views Comparison of Teachers of Govt: Sector and Private sector Universities through Work Experience Regarding Job Satisfaction Domain Company Policies and Practices

Work experience	Universities	N	Mean	Std	t-value
10 years	Govt:	166	16.22	1.22	15.65
	Private	125	11.45	2.77	
11-20 years	Govt:	29	16.11	.11	9.44
	Private	28	12.50	1.23	

The above table 4 reflects views comparison between teachers working in Govt: sector and private sector universities through work experience on company policy and practices. The Mean values of public and private universities teaching faculty of 10 years work experience are 16.22, 11.45, std 1.22, 2.77 respectively. T-value is 15.65. P-value which is .58 is higher than .05 which reflects insignificant difference between the opinions of teaching faculty of 10-year work experience of Govt: and private universities regarding job satisfaction domain company policy and practices. Mean value of public sector universities teaching faculty with 10 years' work experience is 16.22 which shows that teaching faculty with 10 years' work experience of public sector universities are more satisfied than private universities on company policy and practice domain of job satisfaction. The Mean values of public and private universities teaching faculty of 11-20 years' work experience are 16.11, 12.50, std .11, 1.23 respectively. T-value is 9.44. P-value which is .49 is higher than .05 which shows that there is insignificant difference between the opinions of teaching faculty having 11-20-year category work experience of Govt: sector and private sector universities regarding job satisfaction domain company policy and practices. Mean value of public sector universities teaching faculty with work experience 11-20 years is 16.11 which shows that teaching faculty with 11-20 years' work experience of public sector universities are more satisfied than private universities on company policy and practice domain of job satisfaction.

Table 5: Shows views Comparison of Govt: and Private Universities' Teachers on Company Policy and Practices through Age

Age Groups	Universities	N	Mean	std	t-value
30 or below 30 year	Govt:	51	15.44	1.47	7.13

	Private	28	11.22	2.96	
31-50 years	Govt:	144	15.55	1.09	15.11
	Private	126	11.35	2.44	

The above table 5 reflects views contrast between teachers working in Govt: sector and private sector universities through age demographic variable on company policy and practices. The Mean values of public and private universities teaching faculty of 0-30 years age are 15.44, 11.22, std 1.47, 2.96 respectively. T-value is 7.13. P-value which is .77 is higher than .05 which reflects insignificant difference between the opinions of teachers of 0-30-year age of Govt: and private universities regarding job satisfaction domain company policy and practices. Mean values of Govt: and private universities teaching faculty with 31-50 years age is 15.55, 11.33 with std 1.09, 2.44 respectively. T-value is 15.11. P-value which is .55 is higher than .05 which shows that there is insignificant difference between the opinions of teaching faculty having age category 11-20 year of Govt: sector and private sector universities regarding job satisfaction domain company policy and practices. Mean value of Govt sector universities teaching faculty of age category 31-50 is 55.55 which shows that teaching faculty with 31-50 years age category of Govt: sector universities are more satisfied than private universities on company policy and practice domain of job satisfaction.

Discussion

The study is to find out job satisfaction of universities professors in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. In this study job satisfaction domain company policy and practices was focused. The whole research paper is based on this dimension of professor's job satisfaction. In Pakistan higher education institutions are run in both state control as well as in private sector. Those higher education institutions which are financed by state are called public/ Govt: sector institutions. While those institutions which manage their finances in private capacity, is call private sector institutions. Both sector educational institutions are bound under Act/or any other legalization to follow provincial government policies as well as Higher Education Commission of Pakistan. Teacher job satisfaction always remains an issue in Pakistani higher educational institutions. If educators are not satisfied, then their performance may be negatively affected. That's why the researchers were interested to find out job satisfaction of professors. It is usually seen that professor's complaint against university administration. The job of university administration is to implement organizational policy, rules and regulations. The private sector universities are autonomous to maximum level in their finances, discipline, determination of working hours for employees, hiring of teaching faculty, building construction etc. While on the other hand, public sector universities have limited autonomy. These institutions fully follow provincial Govt: as HEC directives in true spirit. Regular audit is carried out of the fund utilization of these institutions. Because these higher education institutions are run by public taxes. In this research paper Govt: sector and private sector universities' professors' job satisfaction has been compared. This comparison has been carried out on company policy and practices domain. Four demographic variables were specified. These variables were academic qualification, designation, work experience, age category.

In this research paper table 2 gives data of comparison by academic qualification on company policy and practices parameter. Academic qualification has been divided in to three categories. These were Master academic qualification, M.Phil/MS , PhD . Insignificant difference was reported among professors by academic qualification on company policy and practices. This insignificant difference reflects that company policy and practices are the same for all the universities' professors and does not make remarkable difference in their job satisfaction. The study is in line with the study of Bholane (2015). He found that university educators are satisfied with their job to moderate level. The researcher has done this study on university educators in Maharashtra state. Table 3 presented that insignificant difference among views of professors of Govt: and private universities on job satisfaction domain company policy and practices by designation. There are four categories of designation of university professors. These categories are Lecturer, Assistant Professor, Associate Professor, Professor. In this paper the first three categories are targeted. This insignificant difference meant that universities rules and regulations are the same for all the professor irrespective of their designation status. The finding of this study regarding designation confirms the finding of the study of Sharma & Jyoti (2009). They (2009) found that there was insignificant difference among views of universities teachers by designation. Sharma & Jyoti study participants were Lecturer, Reader, Professor. They investigated difference among views of these three categories of respondents. One Way ANOVA was employed for the comparison among views of these study participants.

Table 4 gives picture of Govt: and private university professors satisfaction about company policy and practices by work experience. Work experience has been divided into two categories. These work experience categories were 10 or less than 10 years' work experience and 11-20 year. Insignificant difference was reported between Govt: and Private universities' professors' satisfaction about company policy and practices. First the comparison was carried

on work experience category 10 year or less than 10 year between both sector universities' professors. Then comparison was carried on another category which was 11-20-year work experience. In comparison of both categories, insignificant difference was found between professors of Govt: and private sector higher education institutions. This meant that experience did not make remarkable difference among teachers of both sector institutions regarding their organization policies and practices. The findings of the research paper contradict the results of Sharma & Jyoti (2009). They reported significant difference among university teachers by length of service. These scholars had made six categories of length of service and had used ANOVA for analysis of data.

Table 5 gives picture of Govt: and private universities professor satisfaction on organizational policies, rules and regulations by age. Age variable is divided into two groups. These age groups are 30 or less than 30 years, 31 to 50 years. Insignificant difference was reported between satisfaction of Govt: and private universities professors of both age groups. This meant that age group did not make remarkable difference among professors regarding their satisfaction on organizational policies, rules and regulations of both sector higher education institutions. The result of the study contradicts the result of the Malik *et al* (2008). They reported that with increase in age job satisfaction of teachers increased. Age increase positively influenced job satisfaction of professors in Govt: sector universities.

Conclusions

Comparison of the opinions of teaching faculty of public and private universities through selected demographic variables was done regarding company policy and practices domain of job satisfaction. These demographic variables included academic qualification, job designation, work experience. This is concluded that insignificant difference exists between the views of teaching faculty of Govt: sector and private sector university about company policy and practices domain of job satisfaction. The conclusion is that company policy and practices domain of job satisfaction do not differentiate the views of teaching faculty of public and private universities in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

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